

“A Study on ‘Organisational Culture’ and Its Impact on Employees’ Behaviour”

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Abstract

The topic of the project is ‘A Study on ‘Organizational Culture’ and its Impact on employees’ behavior.’ It brings out the behavioral aspect of the employees working for Hyundai Motors India Ltd (HMIL). The main objective of the study is to find the overall performance of the employees.

The purpose of the survey process is to provide a more accurate assessment of the existing culture from the employees’ point-of-view and also to assess their behaviors concerning that of the existing culture.

The culture of an organization consists of the values and beliefs of the people in an organization. The organizational culture usually has values and beliefs that support the organizational goals. Organizational culture has an impact on an employee’s satisfaction.

From the analysis, it was found that the employees of HMIL were much satisfied with their interpersonal relationships, co-ordination and integration between various departments of the organization, and also the rewards & incentives given by their management. But the management has to provide more practical sessions in training programmes to improve their performance in their respective fields. Such training programmes will help them to enhance their knowledge in the respective fields.

Introduction

Automobile Industry

Automobile Industry, the industry that produces automobiles and other gasoline-powered vehicles, such as buses, trucks, and motorcycles. The automobile industry is one of the most important industries in the world, affecting not only the economy but also the cultures of the world. It provides jobs for millions of people, generates billions of dollars in worldwide revenues, and provides the basis for a multitude of related service and support industries. Automobiles revolutionized transportation in the 20th century, changing forever the way people live, travel, and do business.

The automobile has enabled people to travel and transport goods farther and faster and has opened wider market areas for business and commerce. The auto industry has also reduced the overall cost of transportation by using methods such as mass production (making several products at once, rather than one at a time), mass marketing

(selling products nationally rather than locally), and globalization of production (assembling products with parts made worldwide). Between 1886 and 1898, about 300 automobiles were built, but there was no real established industry. A century later, with automakers and auto buyers expanding globally, auto making became the world's largest manufacturing activity, with nearly 58 million new vehicles built each year worldwide.

Objectives of the Study

- To assess the existing culture of the organization and to find its impact on employees' behavior.
- To analyze the overall performance of the employees.
- To learn about the employee's relationship with their peers.
- To study the employees feel about the management.
- To understand how the employer encourages participation in decision making.
- To find out the employees motivational factor.

Research Methodology

Research Design

A research design is an arrangement of condition for collection and analysis of the data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with economy in procedure. The study is descriptive i.e., descriptive research. Descriptive research is concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or group. This includes surveys and fact-finding inquiries of different kinds. The main characteristic of this method is that the researcher has no control over the variables; one can only report what has happened or what is happening. Thus, the research design in case of descriptive study is a comparative design throwing light on all the areas and must be prepared to keep the objectives of the study and the resources available.

Analysis and Interpretation

As the questions generate direct information the data were analyzed using Statistical tools such as,

- Simple percentage
- Weighted average

Percentage Analysis of the Data

Table 1 Employees Have Clear Idea about the Company's Goal

S.No.	Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Strongly Agree	32	32.0
2.	Agree	49	49.0
3.	Neutral	15	15.0
4.	Slightly Disagree	2	2.0
5.	Disagree	2	2.0
	Total	100	100.0

Inferences

From the above table, it is clear that 49% of the respondents agree that they have the clear idea about the company's goal, 32% of the respondents strongly agree, 15% of the respondents are neutral, 2% of the respondents slightly disagreed and 2% of them disagreed.

Table 2 Employees Continuously Track Their Progress Against the Stated Goals

S.No.	Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Strongly Agree	26	26.0
2.	Agree	48	48.0
3.	Neutral	22	22.0
4.	Slightly Disagree	3	3.0
5.	Disagree	1	1.0
	Total	100	100.0

Inference

From the above table, it is clear that 48% of the respondents agree that they continuously track their progress against the stated goals, 26% of the respondents strongly agree, 22% of the respondents are neutral, 3% of the respondents slightly disagreed and 1% of them disagreed.

Table 3 Employees Have a Shared Vision about the Future of Organization

S.No.	Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Strongly Agree	46	46.0
2.	Agree	30	30.0
3.	Neutral	17	17.0
4.	Slightly Disagree	4	4.0
5.	Disagree	3	3.0
	Total	100	100.0

Inference

From the above table it is clear that 46% of the respondents have strongly agreed that they have a shared vision about the future of the organization, followed by 30% of the respondents who agreed, 17% of the respondents are neutral, 4% of the respondents slightly disagreed and 3% of them disagreed.

Table 4 Organization's Vision Creates Motivation for the Employees

S.No.	Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Strongly Agree	25	25.0
2.	Agree	57	57.0
3.	Neutral	10	10.0
4.	Slightly Disagree	3	3.0
5.	Disagree	5	5.0
	Total	100	100.0

Inference

From the above table, it is clear that 57% of the respondents agree that organization's vision creates motivation for them, 25% of the respondents strongly agree, 10% of the respondents are neutral, 3% of the respondents slightly disagreed and 5% of them disagreed.

Weighted Average**Table 1 Opinion about the Organizational Factors with Respect to Employees Behavioral Aspects**

S.No.	Factors	Weightage Score
1.	I am highly involved in my work	4.21
2.	I can manage my work	4.24
3.	The people I work with cooperate to get work done	3.89
4.	My team members have a good interpersonal relationship with me	3.80
5.	My boss consults me on important matters	3.47
6.	My skills and abilities are utilized effectively by the company	3.61
7.	My capabilities are viewed as an important source of competitive advantage	3.49
8.	My work related suggestions are valued	3.50
9.	The organization values diversity	3.67
10.	There is a clear and consistent set of values	3.65
11.	When disagreements occur, I work hard to achieve "win-win" solutions	3.82
12.	It is easy for me to reach consensus, even on difficult issues	3.65
13.	I feel happy to work with people from other parts of the organization also	4.07
14.	It is easy for me to coordinate with different departments of the organization	4.24
15.	I respond well to the organizational changes	4.31
16.	I continually adopt new and improved ways to do work.	4.06
17.	The company's current activities reflect a strong focus on clients	3.79
18.	I am given a real opportunity to improve my skills in this organization	3.82
19.	I view failure as an opportunity for learning and improvement	3.93

20.	There is a clear mission that gives meaning and direction to my work	3.75
21.	I am clear with the organization's long-term purpose and direction	3.90
22.	I have the clear idea about my company's goal	4.07
23.	I continuously track my progress against the stated goals	3.95
24.	I have a shared vision of what the organization will be like in the future	4.12
25.	Organization's vision creates motivation for me	3.94

Inference

From the above table it is clear that most of the respondents gave more weight for the statement “I respond well to the organizational changes”, secondly respondents give more weight for two statements “I have the ability to manage my work & It is easy for me to coordinate with different departments within the organization “, third weight for statement “I am highly involved in my work”, fourth weight for the statement “I have a shared vision of what the organization will be like in the future,” and the fifth position is for two statements “I feel happy to work with people from other parts of the organization also & I have clear idea about my company’s goal”.

Findings

- Sizable number (49%) of the respondents agreed that they have clear idea about the company’s goal.
- Sizable number (48%) of the respondents agreed that they continuously track their progress against stated goals of the company.
- Sizable number (46%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they have shared vision on organization’s future.
- Majority (57%) of the respondents agreed that the organization’s vision creates motivation for them.
- Most of the respondents gave more weight for the statement “I respond well to the organizational changes.”

Suggestions

- In training programmes practical sessions must receive greater emphasize.
- The management may enhance the frequency of employee’s feedback on their performance.
- Now, only the employees who belong to committees can participate in decision-making. The management may encourage all the employees to participate in the decision-making process.

Conclusion

The study about the organizational culture and behavior on employees reveals that the workers were satisfied with their ability, co-operation, team work, involvement, supervisors, utilization of their skills and rewards, etc. They are highly satisfied with the current culture of HMIL. Because of this favorable culture, the employees’ show positive behaviors like high involvement, highly commitment to the organization, highly motivated and highly flexible to the organizational changes, etc.

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